

ПРОФЕСІЙНА ОСВІТА

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Institutional Preconditions for Effective Formation of Officers' International Communication Readiness in Ukrainian Higher Military Education Institutions

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***Abstract.** The article explores the institutional preconditions for the formation of international communication (IC) readiness among officer cadets in Ukrainian higher military educational institutions (HMEIs). The urgency of IC competence is growing in light of Ukraine's Euro-Atlantic integration, NATO interoperability standards, and involvement in multinational defence cooperation.*

***Objective.** This article seeks to examine institutional preconditions by triangulating insights from recent Ukrainian dissertations, theoretical scholarship, and author's empirical data collected through instructor surveys. The purpose is to identify and substantiate the institutional preconditions necessary for the effective formation of IC readiness among officer cadets in Ukrainian HMEIs.*

***Methods.** The methodology is based on document analysis, thematic coding of dissertation content (2018–2024), and empirical findings from an academic staff survey conducted in 2024. The article offers a fourfold classification of institutional preconditions: normative-regulatory, organisational-structural, technological-pedagogical, and value-motivational.*

Results. *The study found that despite normative clarity at the policy level, implementation across HMEIs is inconsistent. Organizational structures often lack cross-departmental coordination. Simulation-based training, Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) methods, and blended learning environments are used sporadically. The motivational domain, influenced by cadets' attitudes, intercultural openness, and institutional culture, remains the least formalized yet critically influential. Educational barriers reported by instructors include the absence of diagnostic tools, limited access to NATO-standard resources, and insufficient integration of language and tactical content.*

Conclusions. *The article concludes with practice-oriented recommendations for institutional reform, including the development of diagnostic instruments, unified governance mechanisms, and pilot modules combining language training with mission-oriented disciplines. The study contributes to the academic and applied discourse on defence education transformation, offering a roadmap for embedding IC competence into Ukraine's military education system.*

Keywords: *international communication, foreign language training; professional military education, officer training, institutional factors, readiness, interoperability, interdisciplinarity, intercultural communicative competence.*

Інституційні передумови ефективного формування готовності офіцерів до міжнародної комунікації у вищих військових навчальних закладах України

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***Анотація.** У статті досліджено інституційні передумови формування готовності до міжнародної комунікації (МК) майбутніх офіцерів у вищих військових навчальних закладах (ВВНЗ) України. Актуальність розвитку компетентності МК зростає в умовах євроатлантичної інтеграції, впровадження стандартів взаємосумісності НАТО та залучення України до багатонаціонального оборонного співробітництва.*

***Метою** статті є дослідження інституційних передумов шляхом триангуляції даних з нещодавніх українських дисертацій, теоретичних досліджень та емпіричних даних автора, зібраних під час опитувань науково-педагогічних працівників, виявлення та обґрунтування інституційних передумов, необхідних для ефективного формування готовності майбутніх офіцерів до МК.*

***Методи.** Методологія дослідження включає аналіз документів, тематичний аналіз дисертаційного матеріалу (2018–2024 рр.) та емпіричні результати опитування науково-педагогічних працівників, проведеного у 2024 році. У статті запропоновано чотирикомпонентну класифікацію інституційних передумов: нормативно-регуляторні, організаційно-структурні, педагогічно-технологічні та мотиваційно-ціннісні.*

***Результати.** Дослідження виявило, що попри наявність нормативної визначеності на рівні політики, практична реалізація у ВВНЗ залишається фрагментарною. Організаційні структури часто бракують міжвідомчої*

координації. Навчання на основі симуляцій, предметно-мовне інтегроване навчання та змішане навчання використовуються спорадично. Мотиваційна сфера – формується настановленнями курсантів, міжкультурною відкритістю та інституційною культурою, що транслюється викладачами – залишається найменш формалізованою, але критично впливовою. Дослідження також виявило бар'єри, про які повідомили викладачі: відсутність діагностичних інструментів, обмежений доступ до ресурсів стандарту НАТО та недостатня інтеграція мовного та тактичного контенту.

Висновки. Стаття завершується практично орієнтованими рекомендаціями щодо інституційної реформи, включаючи розробку діагностичних інструментів, єдиних механізмів управління та пілотних модулів, що поєднують мовну підготовку з місійно-орієнтованими дисциплінами. Дослідження сприяє академічному та прикладному дискурсу щодо трансформації оборонної освіти, пропонуючи дорожню карту для вбудовування компетентності МК у систему військової освіти України.

Ключові слова: міжнародна комунікація, мовна підготовка; військова освіта, підготовка офіцерів, інституційні чинники, готовність, взаємосумісність, міждисциплінарність, міжкультурна комунікативна компетентність.

The Statement of the Problem and Relevance of the Study. In today's strategic context, effective international communication (IC) has become a critical element of military professionalism. Ukraine's integration into Euro-Atlantic security structures, deepening cooperation within NATO, and participation in multinational coalitions and joint initiatives with partner countries demand that future officers of the Armed Forces of Ukraine (AFU) be capable of seamless professional interaction in multicultural and multilingual environments. Accordingly, the ability to act in an

international context – communicatively, culturally, and linguistically – is no longer an optional competency but a core aspect of operational effectiveness.

This institutional demand is clearly articulated in national normative documents regulating officer training. The *Standard of Higher Education for the Field of Knowledge 25 “Military Sciences, National Security, and Border Security”* [1], the *Catalogue of Military Professional Competences* [2], and NATO’s *Language Proficiency Levels Standard (STANAG 6001)* [3] specify the expected outcomes for language, intercultural, and operational competences. These requirements reflect the evolving vision of professional readiness for officers operating in multinational and culturally diverse environments [4]. Of particular importance is the 2018 bachelor-level standard, which explicitly defines learning outcomes such as PR07 – the ability to communicate professionally in a foreign language, and PR08 – the ability to interact effectively with representatives of other professional communities, including foreign military personnel, with attention to terminological and procedural differences.

This strategic demand is echoed in global frameworks. NATO’s Defence Education Enhancement Programme (DEEP) promotes “intellectual interoperability” as a basis for multinational cooperation, supporting reforms in military education that strengthen officers’ linguistic and intercultural competencies [5; 6]. Similarly, the United Nations’ *Action for Peacekeeping (A4P)* initiative identifies language proficiency and cultural awareness as essential prerequisites for peacekeeping effectiveness [7; 8].

Despite this strategic imperative, the educational infrastructure in Ukrainian higher military educational institutions (HMEIs) remains structurally fragmented in addressing IC readiness. Although foreign language courses are formally implemented, they often function in isolation from operational training and fail to simulate realistic professional communication scenarios. Based on the author’s empirical findings, widespread challenges persist: inadequate methodological support, poor coordination

between language and other departments, and a lack of formal institutional policies regulating the development and assessment of IC-related competencies.

Similar concerns are indirectly echoed in recent Ukrainian pedagogical research. For instance, Shorobura and Sevruk [9] refer to the need for interdepartmental alignment in instructional planning when applying case-based learning, while Oliinyk stresses the importance of structured diagnostic procedures in HMEIs [10], although without specific reference to IC-related outcomes. Daniliuk, while focusing on digital language environments in civilian higher education, points to fragmentation in methodological design and the limited integration of communicative tasks – a trend that may be extrapolated to military settings [11].

Recent dissertations in the field of Ukrainian military education reveal systemic institutional and pedagogical barriers to implementing IC training in HMEIs. For instance, Kanova identifies the lack of synchronisation between language policy and actual curriculum design, as well as gaps in methodological support and faculty preparation [12]. Skrypnikova points to structural limitations in the formation of intercultural competence among cadets, emphasising the absence of interdisciplinary integration [13]. Similarly, Krykun documents the shortage of authentic materials, the fragmentation of instructional content, and the non-standardised nature of learning outcomes and assessment procedures related to IC components [14].

Therefore, the issue of institutional preconditions is central: what conditions – normative, organizational, technological, or motivational – enable or inhibit the formation of IC readiness in officer cadets? What structural reforms and pedagogical integrations are needed within HMEIs to support a coherent, practice-based development of this competence?

This article seeks to examine these institutional preconditions through a combination of empirical data (author instructor survey) and a thematic review of recent Ukrainian doctoral dissertations in military pedagogy. The aim is to map the

institutional landscape shaping IC readiness in military officer education and to propose evidence-based recommendations for systemic enhancement.

Analysis of Research and Publications on the Topic. The formation of IC readiness has evolved from a peripheral linguistic concern into a core priority within professional military education (PME). In recent years, this theme has received growing attention in both Ukrainian and international research, underscoring its conceptual complexity and institutional significance. Scholars have increasingly recognised that IC competence is not an auxiliary skill, but a fundamental component of operational effectiveness, leadership development, and multinational interoperability in modern armed forces.

International research provides strong theoretical foundations. The works of Byram [15; 16], Deardorff [17], and Bennett [18] define Intercultural Communicative Competence (ICC) as an integrative construct encompassing linguistic, sociocultural, and behavioural components. These models emphasise the dynamic nature of intercultural interaction and are widely applied in both language education and professional training. In military contexts, institutions such as NATO have adapted these frameworks through initiatives like the DEEP, which positions Cross-Cultural Competence (3C) as a prerequisite for operational interoperability in multinational environments [19; 20].

In Ukrainian military pedagogy, scholarly attention to ICC and IC formation has substantially intensified in recent years. Kanova systematically substantiates the institutional, organisational, and methodological foundations for foreign language training of officers in accordance with NATO's STANAG 6001, proposing an integrated model that encompasses curriculum design, qualification requirements, and instructor training [12]. Skrypnikova presents a comprehensive model of intercultural competence tailored to military leadership training, highlighting its role in fostering adaptive communication, leadership under pressure, and effective teamwork in multinational contexts [13]. Krykun analyses the organisational and methodological

prerequisites for the development of foreign language professional competence, identifying critical gaps in material support, interdepartmental integration, and pedagogical alignment at the strategic level of officer education [14].

Beyond dissertation research, recent Ukrainian scholarly publications have also contributed to the analysis of institutional conditions underpinning communicative and intercultural competence formation. Shorobura and Sevruk examine the application of the case method in developing pedagogical culture among officer cadets, demonstrating its potential for scenario-based learning that simulates real-world communication challenges [9]. Oliinyk presents a conceptual model for diagnostic activities in HMEIs, highlighting the absence of institutionalised mechanisms for assessing communicative outcomes [10]. Daniliuk investigates the digital transformation of foreign language environments, underlining the role of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) in enhancing authenticity and operational relevance in IC-oriented instruction [11].

Other recent dissertations provide valuable applied insights into the integration of IC into various segments of military training. Shalyhina investigates the development of communicative competence among officers of multinational staffs, offering a model of pedagogical support adapted to the communicative demands of NATO-led operations [21]. Savitska [22] and Martynenko [23] focus on interaction skills in aviation and peacekeeping contexts, demonstrating the need to contextualise IC formation within real-life mission scenarios. Arystarkhova addresses the readiness of military instructors, substantiating the importance of targeted training and methodological support for English language and intercultural instruction [24]. Meanwhile, Nanivska [25] and Liubas [26] examine officer training in engineering and combat support branches, respectively, affirming that IC formation must be embedded into the institutional and methodological core of officer education, not confined to standalone language modules.

Despite the growing volume of scholarly work, critical gaps remain unaddressed. One of the most pressing is the limited articulation of institutional integration mechanisms – specifically, how IC formation is structurally embedded within HMEIs, how it is coordinated across academic and operational departments, and how it aligns with real-world professional tasks. Dissertations by Honchar [27] and Kovalchuk [28] underscore the fragmented nature of IC-related initiatives, attributing inconsistency in implementation to the absence of cross-departmental governance models, insufficient faculty development systems, and the lack of standardised diagnostic and assessment instruments.

Unresolved Aspects of the General Problem. Although recent Ukrainian and international studies confirm the strategic importance of IC readiness in military education, several institutional dimensions remain underdeveloped. In particular, there is a lack of systematic analysis of how IC competence is structurally embedded across academic policies, governance frameworks, interdepartmental coordination, and instructor development practices within Ukrainian HMEIs. Existing studies often examine these aspects separately or tangentially, without offering a comprehensive classification of institutional preconditions or linking them to actionable instructional reform. This article addresses these gaps by presenting an integrated, four-dimensional model of institutional preconditions and substantiating it with empirical evidence drawn from national doctoral research and academic staff surveys. The proposed framework contributes a novel, practice-oriented perspective to the evolving discourse on military education transformation.

Purpose and Objectives of the Article. This article seeks to address the identified gaps by triangulating insights from recent Ukrainian dissertations, theoretical scholarship, and the author's empirical data collected through instructor surveys. The aim is to identify institutional configurations that enable or hinder the systemic formation of IC readiness in HMEIs – across governance structures, academic policies, interdepartmental cooperation, and pedagogical practices.

Accordingly, the purpose of this article is to identify and substantiate the institutional preconditions necessary for the effective formation of IC readiness among officer cadets in Ukrainian HMEIs. In the context of Euro-Atlantic integration and operational interoperability with NATO forces, such readiness is no longer limited to language proficiency alone. Rather, it encompasses a complex, multi-level integration of normative, organisational, technological, and pedagogical conditions that shape the capacity of future officers to communicate and interact effectively in multinational military environments.

The relevance of institutional preconditions is twofold. First, they define the structural and resource base of military education systems – whether they include official IC-related learning outcomes, interdepartmental coordination, faculty development programmes, and diagnostic mechanisms. Second, they influence the practical alignment of educational content with the realities of multinational operations – including communication protocols, cultural awareness, and the simulation of operational scenarios in English or other international languages.

This article is guided by the following research objectives:

1. To analyse recent dissertation research and peer-reviewed academic publications in order to identify typical institutional factors that support or hinder the formation of IC readiness in Ukrainian HMEIs.
2. To classify these institutional preconditions into four major categories: normative-regulatory, organisational-structural, technological-pedagogical, and value-motivational.
3. To incorporate expert perspectives gathered through instructor surveys in order to identify perceived systemic barriers and institutional needs related to IC formation in Ukrainian HMEIs.
4. To formulate practice-oriented recommendations for the institutional modernisation of IC formation in Ukrainian military education, drawing on both national policy frameworks and international best practices.

By fulfilling these objectives, the article aims to contribute not only to the theoretical understanding of institutional design for IC competence and IC formation, but also to the practical enhancement of the educational infrastructure that supports Ukraine's officer corps in the context of global defence cooperation.

Presentation of the Main Research Material. Institutional readiness for IC in Ukrainian military education is anchored in a series of national-level normative and doctrinal documents that prioritise language and intercultural training in accordance with NATO benchmarks. Over the last five years, several foundational documents have been adopted that define strategic objectives for linguistic interoperability and officer preparedness for multinational operations.

The *Military Security Strategy of Ukraine* (Decree No. 121/2021) formally recognises language proficiency and IC as components of operational effectiveness in joint missions [29]. The *Strategic Communication Framework for Euro-Atlantic Integration* (Decree No. 348/2021) highlights the need to synchronise communication standards across all levels of the defence sector [30]. Two key doctrinal documents from the Ministry of Defence – the *Language Training Guidelines* [31] and the *Roadmap for Language Training Improvement in the Armed Forces of Ukraine (2021–2025)* – outline mechanisms for aligning officer education with NATO STANAG 6001 [32]. Finally, the *Catalogue of Military Professional Competences* [2] codifies expected learning outcomes, including foreign language skills and the ability to operate in multilingual and multicultural environments.

Furthermore, the *Standard of Higher Education for the Field of Knowledge 25 “Military Sciences, National Security, and Border Security”* [1] includes IC-relevant learning outcomes such as PR07 – the ability to communicate professionally in a foreign language, and PR08 – the ability to collaborate with international actors while accounting for professional, terminological, and cultural differences. Despite this alignment at the level of national policy, the implementation of these requirements across institutions remains inconsistent.

Recent scholarly analyses and doctoral dissertations confirm a persistent gap between formal regulatory mandates and their operationalisation within curricula, instructional practices, and assessment systems [12; 27]. Although NATO-aligned frameworks such as STANAG 6001 are referenced in official documents, HMEIs often lack standardised diagnostic tools, internal accreditation mechanisms, and realistic mission-based evaluation formats for IC components.

Oliinyk outlines a conceptual model for pedagogical diagnostics in military education, emphasising the need for a systematic, institution-wide approach to instructional assessment – though not specifically in the context of IC-related outcomes [10]. In contrast, Nanivska directly addresses the organisational and methodological barriers to integrating NATO-compatible communication models into officer training programmes [25]. These findings suggest that regulatory intent does not always translate into pedagogical implementation.

To summarise, while the Ukrainian defence and education sectors have developed a relatively coherent framework of normative documents in support of IC, their practical institutionalisation in the system of military education remains limited. This persistent gap between policy and implementation calls for targeted structural and procedural adjustments – particularly in curriculum design, interdepartmental governance, and faculty development systems – to ensure that IC-related standards are not only declared, but meaningfully embedded into officer training.

Organisational and structural preconditions refer to the internal governance frameworks, personnel management policies, and interdepartmental coordination mechanisms that determine how IC formation is planned, integrated, and implemented in HMEIs. While regulatory frameworks define strategic priorities, it is institutional governance that operationalises them – translating policy into practice through academic planning, resource allocation, and instructional architecture.

Recent studies reveal several persistent organisational challenges. Many Ukrainian HMEIs lack effective cross-departmental integration of IC-related content.

Foreign language instruction is often confined to language departments and remains largely disconnected from military command training, tactical operations, logistics, or humanitarian disciplines. As a result, cadets rarely engage with military-professional content in English outside of language classes. This compartmentalisation severely undermines contextual transferability – a critical requirement for interoperability in multinational missions.

Studies by Arystarkhova [24] and Honchar [27] reveal that instructional staff in HMEIs are frequently unprepared to support IC formation in operationally relevant contexts. Despite holding formal teaching qualifications, many instructors lack exposure to NATO doctrinal materials, standard operating procedures, and communication formats used in multinational missions. Furthermore, institutional frameworks rarely offer professional development incentives or clear career pathways for faculty who specialise in IC competence training.

Additional evidence from institutional reports and dissertation research indicates a low level of structural innovation in curriculum development [13; 28]. Although some pilot initiatives – such as scenario-based English dialogue courses or modular intercultural training blocks – have been launched, these remain fragmented efforts rather than systemic reforms.

Nanivska highlights the absence of administrative synchronisation between foreign language departments and operational training units, resulting in disjointed methodological planning [25]. Similarly, Shevchenko [33] shows that even when structured stepwise training models exist, IC elements are often underfunded or marginalised as non-core electives. Some institutions have introduced promising models of interdisciplinary integration and modular training. For example, Zaika presents a simulation-based instructional framework that incorporates communicative scenarios into the operational training of future officers [34]. While such initiatives demonstrate significant potential, they often remain confined to isolated departments or temporary projects. Without coordinated leadership and sustainable resource

support at the rectorate or commandant level, these innovations are unlikely to scale or become institutional norms.

In summary, the organisational landscape across Ukrainian HMEIs remains uneven. Although selected institutions have made progress in supporting IC formation through integrated curriculum design and instructional innovation, many continue to operate in fragmented systems. The absence of internal alignment, structured instructor development policies, and cross-functional governance frameworks inhibits the systemic institutionalisation of IC readiness in officer education.

Pedagogical and technological preconditions constitute the methodological foundation for IC formation in HMEIs. These include instructional models, teaching strategies, digital platforms, and cross-curricular integration mechanisms aimed at developing communicative competence in multilingual, multicultural settings. The analysis of dissertation materials and empirical findings indicates that, although various innovations have been introduced, a systematic pedagogical framework for IC support remains underdeveloped.

One of the central challenges lies in the fragmentation of instructional methodologies. Despite the formal adoption of NATO-aligned standards, many HMEIs fail to embed IC-relevant tasks into core disciplinary content. As noted by Krykun [14] and Nanivska [25], foreign language teaching is often isolated from the operational and leadership realities of officer service. Classroom instruction frequently emphasises grammar-focused exercises and generic texts, offering limited exposure to professional simulation or task-based communication practices essential for operational readiness.

However, promising instructional models are emerging. For instance, Zaika presents a simulation-based training framework designed to foster professional competence through communicative scenarios that involve decision-making under conditions imitating operational complexity [34]. The approach incorporates role-play, tactical planning, and performance reflection – elements aligned with NATO's concept of context-driven instruction.

Similarly, Savitska [22] and Martynenko [23] advocate for the use of mission-oriented dialogue simulations in aviation and peacekeeping training environments. These models place cadets in linguistically and culturally dynamic situations that require rapid adaptation, team-based communication, and operational coordination. All three approaches are grounded in the pedagogical logic of task-based learning, scenario-based interaction, and Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL), which collectively support the dual acquisition of professional and communicative competences.

The digitalisation of the training process also opens up new opportunities for enhancing IC formation. As demonstrated by Daniliuk [11], the integration of virtual language environments and learning management systems (LMS) enables cadets to engage with authentic materials and operationally relevant formats – including NATO briefings, multilingual standard operating procedures (SOPs), and real-time military communication feeds. This technological infrastructure creates a simulated immersion effect that supports the transfer of language skills into mission-oriented contexts.

Nanivska developed a blended model combining web-based quests with classroom instruction to build communicative competence among future engineering officers [25]. Her approach integrates scenario-based digital modules with reflective feedback cycles, contributing to learners' adaptability in field-specific communication.

Polonskyi, in turn, highlights the value of embedding research-oriented tasks into IC instruction [35]. By requiring cadets to analyse mission scenarios, synthesise cultural intelligence, and reflect on communication breakdowns, such methods enhance both linguistic awareness and strategic thinking, reinforcing IC as a cross-cutting professional competence.

Meanwhile, Arystarkhova [24] and Liubas [26] emphasise the critical role of instructor development and didactic resource design in the systemic formation of IC competence. The effectiveness of IC-oriented training largely depends on whether instructors are provided with detailed methodological guidance, granted access to

NATO-standardised instructional materials, and involved in co-developing interdisciplinary content that spans language, tactical, and leadership domains. This intersection between pedagogical capacity and institutional infrastructure remains a decisive factor in the sustainability and scalability of IC implementation across HMEIs.

Collectively, these studies suggest that task-based models, simulation technologies, blended learning formats, and instructor development must be treated as institutional priorities if IC readiness is to be realised at scale. Without coordinated technological and methodological support, policy mandates and strategic objectives are unlikely to be translated into operationally relevant learning experiences for cadets.

While institutional, organisational, and technological preconditions define the structural architecture and delivery systems of IC training in HMEIs, the formation of IC readiness also depends on a stable value-motivational foundation. This dimension includes cadets' attitudes toward international engagement, their willingness to operate in multilingual environments, and their intrinsic motivation to become competent communicators in multinational military operations.

Survey data collected by the author in 2024 among 61 instructors from various departments of Ukrainian HMEIs indicates that, while cadets generally understand the strategic importance of IC, their intrinsic motivation to develop corresponding competences is perceived as inconsistent. According to instructor assessments, many cadets view foreign language study as a formal requirement rather than a functional skill for professional interaction. Furthermore, a significant proportion of educators noted that cadets often demonstrate low levels of intercultural openness, with discomfort or hesitation when placed in multilingual or multicultural learning contexts.

These findings are consistent with conclusions drawn from academic research. Skrypnikova argues that intercultural competence cannot be cultivated solely through instructional input – it must be grounded in attitudinal openness, value-based reflection, and authentic personal engagement. Her dissertation confirms that

sustainable IC formation depends on internalised dispositions that extend beyond the classroom [13].

Similarly, Martynenko demonstrates that cadets' motivation for international communication is shaped not only by educational content, but also by peer influence, leadership role models, and participation in authentic intercultural tasks such as collaborative projects and mission simulations [23]. These social and experiential factors significantly enhance openness to diversity and communication confidence.

Dissertations by Liubas [26] and Honchar [27] further emphasise the importance of institutional culture and command climate in shaping cadet motivation. In environments where commanding officers and instructors explicitly model intercultural openness, cadets exhibit higher levels of engagement and reflective awareness. Conversely, in units where IC training is undervalued or treated as a secondary task, cadets are less likely to perceive its relevance to professional identity and career development.

Additional insights from recent pedagogical studies reaffirm the importance of attitudinal and value-based engagement in officer education. Shorobura and Sevruc [9], for instance, demonstrate how case-based instructional formats can stimulate cadet motivation and reflexive thinking, especially when addressing complex interpersonal dynamics and ethical challenges in military group settings. Although not explicitly framed in terms of intercultural competence, such methods create conditions conducive to developing communication awareness and pedagogical responsibility.

Nanivska, in turn, underscores the integration of value education within communicative training, emphasising the formation of professional identity around the ideals of intercultural respect, solidarity, and service in multinational settings [25].

Taken together, these perspectives indicate that value-motivational preconditions for IC readiness extend beyond instructional design. They require institutional role modelling, ethically anchored curricula, and learning environments that support reflective exploration of personal and cultural assumptions. Only through

such a multidimensional, value-driven approach can officer cadets internalise the dispositions needed for confident, competent participation in international defence cooperation.

Conclusions and Prospects for Further Research. The conducted analysis confirms that the formation of IC readiness in Ukrainian HMEIs is not merely a linguistic or methodological task. Rather, it is a multidimensional process shaped by a complex of institutional preconditions – including normative alignment, organisational capacity, pedagogical innovation, and value-based motivation – that must be simultaneously addressed.

First, the **regulatory foundation** for IC readiness is generally well-articulated at the national level. Ukraine's strategic documents align with NATO standards and formally include IC-related learning outcomes in PME. However, their practical translation into programme content, learning activities, and assessment procedures remains uneven, often reduced to declarative inclusion.

Second, the **organisational and structural preconditions** reveal substantial fragmentation. Many HMEIs lack established mechanisms for interdepartmental cooperation, coordinated curriculum development, and instructor support for interdisciplinary IC training. As a result, efforts remain siloed and inconsistent, limiting institutional capacity for systemic reform.

Third, **pedagogical and technological approaches**, including simulation-based instruction, CLIL models, and blended learning formats, show increasing potential for contextualised and mission-oriented IC development. Nevertheless, these innovations remain under-institutionalised and highly dependent on individual instructors' initiative and support from local leadership.

Finally, the **value-motivational dimension** appears to be the least formalised but arguably the most influential in shaping cadets' communicative readiness. Without institutional cultures that model intercultural openness, ethical leadership, and

reflective practices, even the most advanced instructional models are unlikely to generate operationally relevant outcomes.

These findings suggest that the formation of IC readiness requires a **comprehensive and synchronised institutional strategy** that integrates all four dimensions. Future research should focus on the development of assessment tools to evaluate institutional IC capacity, empirical validation of interdisciplinary training modules, and comparative studies of IC integration practices across NATO-aligned defence education systems. Equally important is the exploration of leadership-driven mechanisms for promoting institutional cultures that normalise international communication as a defining aspect of military professionalism.

To address the identified gaps and sustain progress in IC formation, future research should focus on the following priorities:

- developing a national model for institutionalising IC readiness that integrates normative, organisational, pedagogical, and motivational dimensions;
- designing and validating diagnostic tools to assess structural, instructional, and value-based IC capacity across military academies;
- piloting interdisciplinary modules and integrated training scenarios involving both foreign language instruction and core military subjects;
- evaluating command culture and its influence on cadet motivation, intercultural openness, and communicative resilience;
- comparing Ukrainian institutional practices with exemplary IC training models adopted in NATO member states.

Such research efforts will contribute to the development of a cohesive, mission-oriented ecosystem of IC training – one that fosters not only linguistic and intercultural competence, but also strategic communicative readiness for Ukrainian officers operating in international environments.

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